

SIMPLIFIED FRONTEND FOR DATA GENERATION AND TESTING PURPOSES IN WINCC OA.

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

This project was supported by the BE/ICS/Frameworks and Development section at CERN.

As the first step, a Simplified Frontend should be designed to replace the existing Future NextGen Archiver frontend for testing purposes. The Simplified Frontend would act as an interface to connect to the backend. This connection to the backend is necessary in order to complete the following tasks:

1. Functional testing of the backend: Through this project, both existing as well as upcoming features of backend would be tested. The testing process can be classified into steps as follows: identification of functions the backend is expected to perform, creation of input data to test these functions, determination of output of backend to these inputs, execution of the written tests and eventually comparison of the expected and the actual response of the backend.
2. Data generation for non-functional/performance testing of the backend: This involves designing a tool that simulates value changes that occur in data points as they would have in effect occurred in experiments. This includes studying the distribution of features in the data from experiments like frequency of occurrence and range of data points. The challenge is to simulate data points with a huge range of frequency ranging from a millisecond up to five years. Further, for the implementation, it is also necessary to have an understanding of data rates supported by the backend. The parameters like begin time and end time of data generation should be specified in the configuration file, which makes it easy to use the data generator without any intervention in the code.

ABSTRACT

Future NextGen Archiver, a research and development project of WinCC OA, is a joint collaboration of ETM Siemens and CERN. It supports multiple backends including a BigData backend using Apache Kudu as storage. For the completion of this project, a simplified frontend was designed which communicates via an external interface using ZeroMQ and Protocol Buffers (ProtoBuff) with the BigData backend. The data generator and tester are designed as plugins to independently use this interface to connect to the backend. The main purpose for data generator is to generate data that can be used for performance tests for different retrieval scenarios in this BigData backend. These scenarios include getting value changes over a period for a few signals specified by name or alias. It can be used to get value changes over a specified duration for many signals (possibly hundreds of thousands) specified by complex filters on metadata fields (like device name, location, type). Further, it can also be used to get values of all signals at start time and then replay value changes till the end time. The data generator was efficiently implemented using sorting and accumulation algorithms. As a result new values are produced by it at a rate such that data generation is not a bottleneck when compared with later stages of processing. The backend functional tester uses google tests in C++ 11 to perform functional testing of Kudu backend. It tests for response of backend under varied conditions of creation, modification and deletion of metadata and creation/duplication of data.

As a result, functional testing for the backend and environment setup (data generation) for non-functional/performance testing of the backend were favourably completed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

WinCC OA is a Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition System (SCADA) designed by ETM, a subsidiary of Siemens. It is widely used by all 4 major experiments at CERN and the BE/ICS group. Future Next Gen Archiver is a research and development subproject of WinCC OA. Future NextGen Archiver is a joint collaboration of ETM and CERN.

Future Next Gen Archiver will support multiple backends including Oracle Backend, Big Data backend and a Streaming Backend. It could be adapted easily to support other backends as well. For this project which aims to develop testing tools, Big Data backend using Apache Kudu as storage was used.

Figure 1: Future Next Gen Archiver architecture

2. SIMPLIFIED FRONTEND ARCHIVER ARCHITECTURE

For the scope of this project, Future Next Gen Archiver was replaced by a Simplified Frontend. It acts as an external interface to connect to the Backend Archiver and hence the Apache Kudu cluster. It uses ZeroMQ as the messaging library to connect to the backend. Further, it uses Protocol buffers (ProtoBufs) for serializing structured data to be sent via ZeroMQ.

In this architecture, the generator and tester are designed as plugins and can independently connect to the backend using the Simplified Frontend. They perform the following functions:

1. Generator plugin: This was designed to setup environment for non-functional/performance testing of the Backend. This generates mock data which simulates in effect the actual data produced by experiments which use the NextGen Archiver.

- Tester plugin: The aim for designing tester plugin was to perform functional testing of the existing features of the backend. At the same time it implemented tests for scenarios not currently supported by the backend but would be supported in the future.

Figure 2: Simplified Frontend Architecture

3. DESIGN FEATURES

a. BACKEND TESTER

The unique features of backend tester design are:

- Direct reading connection with Apache Kudu cluster.
- Test cases are written using Google Test thereby supporting running a specific test rather than running all tests each time. Test cases use features of EXPECT and ASSERT from Google Test.
- Fully implemented matcher functions that can be used to compare data structures like data point lists and metadata identifiers which are commonly used in backend.
- Functions to compare expected string with reference logs received from backend.
- Tester can be used to create single threaded and/or multi-threaded tests.

b. DATA GENERATOR

The generator plugin is capable of producing data points with the following characteristics:

- The frequency of changes for each data point is randomly chosen from a range of a millisecond to five years using Gaussian distribution.
- Data points of all data types currently supported by the Kudu Backend are generated i.e primitive types, strings, time.
- The value of each data point is randomly chosen from a range using uniform distribution.
- Data is generated for a period specified in the configuration file, possibly from a date in the past to a date in the future.

- String values are generated from permutation of an inbuilt dictionary of words generated once for each file.

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF DATA GENERATOR

Figure 3: Implementation of Config Generator and Simplified Frontend

a. READ METADATA FILE

The input to the generator is a CSV metadata file containing data point name, data point id, unit, alias and comment. Data point name is extracted from this file which is also a field present in the message sent through data channel. Further, the data type is deduced using the data point name i.e the data point name is scanned to search if it contains particular keywords. For instance,

Keyword present in data point name	Deduced data type
“bool”	Boolean
“string”	Text
“analog”	Unsigned 32 bit integer
“counter”	Signed 32 bit integer
“time”	Time
“double”	Double
default	Signed 32 bit integer

b. CREATE JSON FILE

A JSON file is created which contains an entry corresponding to each entry read from the metadata file. Each entry in this file has data point name, id, alias, comment, unit and most significantly a maximum and minimum value which signifies the range of values that particular data point can have. This range is randomly selected from a set of predefined ranges. The set of predefined ranges is chosen so as to simulate data points covering a variety of ranges like large positive and negative numbers, only large negative numbers, only large positive numbers, smaller positive and negative numbers and so on. Each entry also has its frequency of generation which is randomly selected. The task of Config generator is completed at this stage and the generated JSON file is used by the Simplified Frontend as input in further steps.

c. CONFIGURATION CHANNEL CONNECTION

In Simplified Frontend, Configuration channel connection is established to send metadata. The list of entries to be sent is compared with the list of entries already present in the storage and only the difference of these lists is sent via the configuration channel to avoid multiple entries of the same data point in the metadata table.

d. GENERATE DATA TO BE SENT

As a pre-processing step, data points are sorted based on their frequency. This is important because data points have a large range of frequencies ranging from 1 millisecond to five years. Further, for each generated data point a value is chosen from its specified range. These data points are accumulated until a block size (specified in the configuration file) is attained.

e. DATA CHANNEL CONNECTION

Data channel connection is established to send data. The duration for which data points are to be generated can be specified in the configuration file. Messages are accumulated until a block size is attained and then sent to the backend, followed by clearing the list and same process is repeated for the entire duration of time specified.

5. PROJECT SUMMARY

a. CONCLUSION

i. Results for data generator

- The data generator simulates value changes in data points at an average rate of 5,000,000 for a simulated time duration of one second.
- The start time and end time for which the data is to be generated can be specified in the configuration (INI format) file.
- The Config Generator takes as input a metadata file which generates as output a JSON file located in the Simplified Frontend directory. This JSON file can be used independently in the future for any other purpose if needed.
- Data generator is designed as a plugin which independently uses frontend interface to connect to the backend.
- The data generated by the Simplified Frontend can be used to test several use cases like:
 1. Trending: get value changes over a period for a few signals specified by name or alias.
 2. Event screen: get value changes over period of time for many signals (around hundreds of thousands) specified by complex filters on metadata.
 3. Event replay: get values of all signals at replay start time, then get all value changes in replayed period.

ii. Results for Backend Functional Tester

The testing of backend was successfully completed. The response of backend was tested on following test cases:

- All data types: signed/unsigned integer/long integer, character, bits, text and time are supported by backend.
- Bad status reply when duplicate/already existing data points (same data point name and timestamp) are sent to backend via the data channel.
- New entries are accurately created, modified and deleted in the metadata table.
- Error when duplicate metadata entry is sent to backend.

b. FUTURE WORK

i. Data Generator

- Currently the data generator supports only data point changes, further it may be extended to simulate real time metadata changes as well.
- Data Generator can be extended to be compatible with all formats of metadata files.

- Data Generator can be run on several virtual machines simultaneously to test the throughput of the backend with the data being produced.

ii. Backend Functional Tester

- Tests can be added to check for interactions with metadata delta updates.
- As more features are added to the Backend, corresponding test cases can be added to the tester as well.

